

NELTA ELT Forum

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Teaching EFL Vocabulary through the DCR Model: A Sample Teacher-Training Workshop

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Abstract

Vocabulary teaching remains a persistent challenge for EFL teachers in rural, resource-constrained schools, where learners rely heavily on their teachers as the primary source of English input. This practice-based article outlines a professional development workshop designed to support in-service EFL teachers in building a practical repertoire of vocabulary presentation techniques. Structured around the Discussion, Construction, and Reflection (DCR) model and grounded in social practice theory, the workshop guides participants through eliciting existing instructional practices, collaborative hands-on demonstration, and context-specific reflection. Participants learn techniques that require low-cost to no-cost materials, ranging from realia and board drawings to contextual examples and hanging cards. Teacher educators working in similar low-resource contexts may find the DCR model a flexible, replicable framework that can be adapted to different class sizes, word types, and local conditions.

Keywords: DCR model, EFL vocabulary instruction, rural teacher training, social practice theory, professional development

Introduction

Drawing on professional experience in rural Nepal, the author has observed that vocabulary instruction is a major challenge for teachers in basic-level EFL classrooms. Students encounter numerous unfamiliar words daily; however, many teachers rely primarily on pedagogical strategies such as repetition drills, translation exercises, and rote memorisation. Sole reliance on textbook materials, limited access to multimedia resources, and minimal exposure to English outside the classroom contribute to students' overreliance on teachers for lexical acquisition. This reliance imposes a significant burden on educators, whose opportunities for professional development often remain limited.

Traditional approaches to vocabulary instruction, such as isolated word lists and rote translation, often fail to deepen understanding and support retention in an engaging and participatory way. Thornbury (2002) proposes that when teachers mediate and expose learners to authentic (literary) texts, learners' vocabulary repertoire develops due to cognitive engagement with words. Schmitt (2008) emphasises that vocabulary develops when learners are allowed to engage with target language items repeatedly and actively. In addition, Nation (2022) argues that effective vocabulary learning requires that teachers present words in meaningful linguistic contexts. Therefore, teachers are recommended to pay close attention when tailoring their vocabulary presentation strategies for EFL learners.

The DCR model-based professional development workshop described in this article aligns with Freeman's (2009) social practice theory, while some of the strategies discussed in the workshop are adapted from Doff's (1988) vocabulary teaching strategies. Drawing upon sociocultural learning theories, including activity theory and communities of practice, Freeman (2009) conceptualises social practice – such as teacher learning – as a process through which participants interpret meaning via engagement in shared activities over time. Participants pursue mutually recognised goals using both physical and symbolic tools, such as instructional materials, strategies, and dialogue. This dynamic interaction among tools, activities, and participants' roles is exemplified by the application of the DCR model to design vocabulary instruction strategies for EFL learners.

The Discussion stage of the DCR model incorporates Freeman's (2009) concept that an activity is influenced by prior actions (history) and participants' expectations of what will come (emergent) (p. 5). Accordingly, two activities are described in the Discussion stage to activate participants' prior knowledge and prompt reflection on future steps in vocabulary presentation techniques. Similarly, during the construction stage, tools, activities, and participant roles are aligned with Freeman's value propositions of effectiveness and durability (2009, p. 6). The two activities in this stage are exemplified by demonstrative and collaborative approaches that embody these principles and deliver long-term impact, especially in resource-constrained environments. Finally, the reflection stage comprises two activities evaluated through the lens of whether the tools, activities, and roles foster a personal and generative process (Freeman, 2006, p. 6). Participants critically reflect on the techniques practised, considering their applicability within their specific teaching contexts, and develop lesson plans tailored to their individual needs.

The following section presents the workshop in full, organised by stage with suggested time allocations.

Workshop Title: Teaching EFL vocabulary through the DCR model

Duration: 90 minutes

Participants: Basic-level EFL teachers in rural community schools

Materials required: Printed worksheets, whiteboard, markers, and a few real objects

Objectives:

- To identify and evaluate existing techniques of presenting vocabulary to EFL learners.
- To practice a variety of vocabulary presentation techniques through demonstration and guided practice.
- To reflect on how these techniques can be adapted to participants' own classroom contexts.

Workshop Stages:

Stage 1: Discussion (25 minutes)

In this initial stage, the facilitator provides opportunities for participants to articulate their current vocabulary instruction strategies. The objective is to identify their existing knowledge and practices and to establish a foundation for subsequent workshop activities.

Activity 1: Eliciting existing practices (10 minutes)

The facilitator opens the workshop by dividing participants into pairs or small groups and posing a single reflective question: "What are the possible ways of introducing vocabulary to your students?" Participants first discuss in pairs and share their findings. The facilitator jots down their answers on the Whiteboard without evaluation, prompting them to reflect on their own teaching. This shared inventory of strategies gives the facilitator a clear picture of what the group already knows and where the gaps lie.

Activity 2: Comparing two presentation techniques (15 minutes)

The facilitator writes the word "*tumble*" on the board and provides its Nepali equivalent; participants repeat it in chorus. The facilitator then writes "*crumble*" and, instead of translating it, uses it in a short English sentence to clarify its meaning, e.g., "The building crumbled after the explosion." The facilitator provides additional example sentences to help participants master the word by asking them to say it in Nepali. Participants are asked to discuss which approach they found more useful and why. The facilitator establishes that the former is the simplest and clearest way to show the meaning of words; however, the latter offers more contextual usage, as the examples show how the word is used in English.

Stage 2: Construction (40 minutes)

In this stage, the facilitator and participants co-construct knowledge and skills through hands-on demonstration and guided collaborative practice. Each technique is first modelled by the facilitator and then practised by participants.

Activity 3: Demonstrating vocabulary presentation techniques (20 minutes)

In this stage, the facilitator models the following activities to present vocabulary, laying the groundwork for co-constructing knowledge with the participants.

Real objects: The facilitator writes a few words, e.g., *book*, *pen*, *watch*, on the board. Then s/he holds up one of the objects written on the board, e.g., a book, and, pointing out, tells the participants what it is; s/he asks them to repeat it. And when they correctly name the object, he thanks them with positive feedback. Participants then practice in pairs with other real objects available in the classroom. At the end, s/he notes that the value of this technique lies in its immediacy; connecting a word directly to a tangible object removes ambiguity and eliminates the need for translation.

Drawings: The facilitator writes these words on the board: *tree, tractor, cow*. Then, s/he sketches a tree and checks participants' understanding by asking them to identify the word drawn in the picture. If time allows, s/he can invite the participants to draw other objects and practice the technique with the whole group. S/he reminds the participants that this technique is particularly useful for teaching concrete nouns that cannot be brought into the classroom.

Mime: The facilitator writes the words 'sneeze,' 'dig,' and 'running' on the board. S/he mimics an action, such as sneezing, then says the word 'Sneezing'. S/he asks the participants to repeat the word, and if they do so correctly, says, 'Yes, that's correct – sneezing!' offering positive feedback. The participants then take turns miming other words in pairs. S/he also explains that this technique is particularly useful for teaching action verbs and facial expressions because it encourages active participation and helps learners connect movements with words.

Contextual examples: The facilitator writes two words on the board, 'kind' and 'brave', and presents each in a short, simple sentence: "A kind person always helps others. Our teacher is very kind." S/he then invites the participants to construct their own sentences for bravery using a similar pattern. S/he explains that this technique works best for abstract adjectives and concepts that cannot be shown physically, helping learners infer meaning from context.

After presenting the above techniques, the facilitator establishes that for objects that are both tangible and can be brought into the classroom, the real objects technique can be used. In contrast, for objects that cannot be brought into the classroom, drawings can be used. And, for action words and facial expressions, miming could be the best alternative. Likewise, for complex concepts, abstract ideas, and contextual explanations, the best approach. If resources allow, participants can use 8-inch hanging cards or 4-inch × 4-inch flashcards to present words, either by drawing a picture and naming it at the bottom of the hanging card, or by writing the word and its corresponding meaning on the front and back of the flashcard. Lastly, participants can also combine multiple techniques to best present the vocabulary items being taught.

Activity 4: Guided group practice (20 minutes)

Participants worked in small groups. The facilitator distributes the printed worksheets from Appendix A to each group. Each group decides which presentation technique is most appropriate for each word and provides the underlying reasoning for their choice. After deciding on the technique, they present it to the members of their neighbouring group and exchange their handouts to give feedback and learn from each other. The facilitator moves around during practice, providing support to each group and, at the end, offering feedback on the choices made to the whole group.

Stage 3: Reflection (25 minutes)

In this stage, the applicability of practised techniques is explored in greater depth through collective reflective discussion and context-specific lesson planning. Here, the participants understand which strategies they have learned and how to apply them.

Activity 5: Critical Reflection and Mini-lesson planning (25 minutes)

The facilitator asks the following lead-in question and invites participants to reflect on working in small groups: Which of the techniques demonstrated would work best in your classroom? What challenges might you face in using them? How could you adapt the techniques considering your materials and students? He allows about five to seven minutes to ponder these questions. Once they are done, he asks the groups to share their key points. During this, the facilitator facilitates and assists them in making connections across the ideas.

Following the reflection discussion, the facilitator invites each group to prepare a brief mini-lesson plan outlining how they will apply one of the techniques practised in their new lesson. The mini-lesson plan should include: the word (s) to be taught, the chosen technique, the estimated time, and one anticipated challenge and how it will be addressed. Groups then share their lesson plans with the whole group. The facilitator offers constructive feedback on each plan, highlighting strengths and suggesting minor adaptations if needed. Eventually, the facilitator wraps up the workshop, thanking participants for their active participation.

Conclusion

The DCR model presents a theoretically grounded and practically accessible framework for training EFL teachers in low-resource environments. Participants utilise both physical tools (e.g., teaching materials) and symbolic tools (e.g., pedagogical strategies) to develop proficiency in vocabulary presentation activities through collaborative practice with colleagues and facilitators (Freeman, 2009). Moreover, the activities outlined in this workshop are designed to require no technological resources, are adaptable to various types of words, and can be readily implemented in the classroom. Importantly, given that this workshop is tailored for low-resource contexts, practitioners can modify it to accommodate class size, learners' proficiency levels, available materials, and local languages. Future teacher development initiatives could incorporate classroom observations or follow-up reflections to evaluate the implementation of these techniques in actual teaching scenarios.

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Appendix

Vocabulary List for Activity Four

No.	Word	Technique Choice (RO/D/M/CE/Others)	Reasoning
1	Window		

2	Jump		
3	Kind		
4	Pen		
5	Run		
6	Lazy		
7	Elbow		
8	Dance		
9	Brave		
10	Mountain		
11	Sleep		
12	Beautiful		
13	Desk		
14	Laugh		
15	Intelligent		

Legend

RO = Real Objects | D = Drawings | M = Mime | CE = Contextual Examples | Others = Hanging cards/Flash cards or a combination of multiple techniques (please specify the combined techniques).